

**UNIVERSITY OF THE PHILIPPINES
OPEN UNIVERSITY**

MASTER OF ENVIRONMENT AND NATURAL RESOURCES MANAGEMENT

HANNAH JEAN RIPARIP JUGUILON

**THE ROLE OF WOMEN IN THE FISHERY INDUSTRY OF
SAN FABIAN, PANGASINAN, PHILIPPINES**

Special Problem Adviser:

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Faculty of Management and Development Studies

02 February 2024

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DECLARATION

This is to certify that:

- I. The Special Problem comprises only my original work towards the MENRM except where indicated in the Preface
- II. Due acknowledgment has been made in the text to all other material used
- III. The special problem is fewer than 25,000 words in length, exclusive of tables, maps, bibliographies, and appendices.

HANNAH JEAN RIPARIP JUGUILON

Name

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Abstract

The roles of women fisherfolk are often limited to processing and marketing only. Apart from these, other roles in the pre and actual fishing and aquaculture operation are often overlooked and unrecognized. This paper identifies other significant roles that women contribute to the value-chain of fisheries as well as their roles as wives and mothers that make the fishing community and the industry stable. Sixteen women fisherfolk from three (3) barangays in San Fabian were interviewed as key stakeholders using a questionnaire that focused on their daily work, their duties as housewives, the production costs, profits gained, their experiences and their plans for their families.

These roles were classified into four (4) major sectors in the fisheries industry, namely, 1) capture fisheries, in gathering of fish and shellfish, installation of fish traps, net mending, boat managers; 2) aquaculture sector composed of fish culture, preparation of materials for fish pens, feeding of stocks; 3) processing sector composed of fish salting and drying, fish deboning and marinating; and 4) fish vending or marketing, composed of selling fresh and processed fish. From the four (4) sectors mentioned, dried fish vending and fish processing sectors were more profitable than capture fisheries and aquaculture. The aquaculture sector required less laborious operation during the feeding period, however it took longer days of culture period and higher cost of inputs such as the cost of fingerlings, cost of nets and bamboo and additional feeds, if necessary. The capture fisheries sector for the municipal fishery has its daily income guaranteed, however, it was more laborious and riskier during the fishing operation. Hence, the fish processing, dried fish vending and aquaculture operation required higher cost of capital but guarantees higher profit; while capture

fisheries and fresh fish vending for retailers required less capital, daily income return but lesser profit earned.

Further, each sector entailed skills that the women fisherfolk have gained through their families and the availability of resources in their environment. These factors influenced their involvement in each sector, aside from the considerations on how profitable their livelihood was.

The common issues encountered by these women were low catch, difficulty in transport and marketing of their goods, unstable income source, housing and health facilities, source of capital and education privileges. Some of the government and non-government interventions were cited to address these issues.

Considering the workload that women do in helping the fisheries industry prosper, they have multiple burdens. Accomplishing their added obligations as a mother to their children and as wife to their husbands make the work of these women fisherfolk very necessary and noteworthy to the fishing industry through their unpaid work.

These roles and their involvements in each sector will help to identify proper interventions, to help build a more empowered workforce in the fisheries trade and make them good managers of the aquatic resources of their localities.

Keywords: women fisherfolk, significant roles, key stakeholders, major sectors

I. INTRODUCTION

The Municipality of San Fabian is a coastal municipality in the province of Pangasinan. Among the 34 barangays, there are 15 coastal barangays making the fishing industry a very significant source of income and livelihood for the residents. Fisheries post-harvest industry in San Fabian is also an important part of livelihood for its residents and fish drying is one of its major products, particularly the “tuyo” or dried fish wherein the role of women is highlighted. Apart from this, women also perform a big part in the field of aquaculture, capture, processing, and fish vending industry.

Oftentimes, the efforts of women in the fishery industry are unrecognized. Because of the stereotype that the work in fisheries is for men since it requires laborious, heavy workload and risky conditions especially in the capture fisheries sector. Nevertheless, the world is continually changing, and these women efforts are gradually recognized through the onset of Gender equality, Gender, and Development, among others that is always incorporated in government interventions, private agencies, and non-government organizations.

Research and studies focusing women’s role on the fishery industry should also be well-explored and backed up by actual scenarios especially in coastal localities to further plot these roles into data and information necessary to justify and craft policies that will benefit the women sector, since they play a very important role not just in the fishery industry and food security but also for every Filipino family in the country.

According to Rabbit et al. (2019), promoting sustainable resource use projects to achieve food security must include women’s participation through giving access to information and strategies for effective implementation. To have a picture of how the communities in coastal areas relate to the fishing industry, the role of women in the

management of fisheries resources must be incorporated. This will facilitate a better understanding and improve resource management to achieve food security. In the Pacific, womenfolk are deeply immersed in fisheries. Their harvest is significant, and the influence of this production must sufficiently be one of the factors in resource management plans if maintainable production and improved food security is the aim. Aside from considering women's harvest in view of its effect in the environment, it must be noted that the providers of seafood in the diet of the household are women. As principal managers of the food supply in the household, it is vital that information and strategies posted by such projects be accessible to women.

II. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Bradford and Katikiro (2019) stated that in Tanzania, women performing works in fisheries and aquaculture must be acknowledged to break down the cultural and economic barriers, achieve effective gender-based policy and fair access of men and women to fisheries resources.

The qualitative data from the study of Zhao et.al. (2013), in England, seemed to verify that women are frequently under-represented, unrecognized, unpaid, or underpaid and appear to have minimum involvement in decision and policy making at different stages in the fishing commerce. Significant part of the study was the part of the unseen workforce of women who participated to the persistence of the fishing commerce by unpaid provision of their spouses for being responsible in paper works, establishing small businesses and facilitating daily functions of the entire operation. Women were excepted not just because they have unpaid recognition or rights for retirement fund, but they were unnoticed too, throughout consultations on policy changes by the government. Taking advantage of the authentic pursuit in the viability of the industry, consequently, their families and livelihood is apparently the most productive way in rising the awareness and participation of women.

Roles of Women in Fisheries

In the study of Harper et al. (2013), women play the role from catching and processing fish, nutrition and food security to sale and finance. The determination of these roles from Europe, Africa, America, Asia, and Oceania lead to recommendations of management policies composed of improved utilization of women's ecological knowledge regarding biodiversity, conservation, and climate change; fisheries

economies; gathering of data for gender-specific fisheries participation, decision-making, linkages, health, and poverty alleviation.

Calhoun et.al. (2016), state that wives of fishermen support elderly groups in managing business endeavors in fishing, engaging with shifting markets, progressively intricate regulations, and daily tasks of taking care of the family. Women are immensely part of the manpower in the system of fisheries despite the stereotype that it is still mainly assumed as a male-dominated industry. Women in fishing communities demonstrated their contribution to the social capital and regularly leads advocacy efforts of their groups. Fisheries leaders, decision and policy makers in state and federal agencies have greater likelihood of crafting strategies that lessen harmful economic and social impacts to fishing groups through incorporating the roles of women. These are also achieved by making sure that their contributions are visible.

Results from the study of Shah and Bukhari (2019) showed that women participation is observed throughout majority of areas of culture period in aquaculture industry such as fish feeding, retail marketing, small-scale processing, ownership of the pond, net mending, boat rowing, pond construction, feed manufacturing and ornamental fish culture. In fishing communities, women play multi-dimensional roles and their participation in value chains of fisheries are frequently regarded as obscure even though they are active in broad range of occupations in capture fisheries and aquaculture. Aside from this, they are also involved in generating additional income and maintaining their families. The tasks performed by women in Gambian fishery are not constrained to Gambia alone but as well as West-Africans Sub-region.

Women Involvement in Decision-Making

Women frequently lead the role in advocating the welfare of fishing communities (Calhoun et al. 2016). Decision-making processes showcasing women's voices may improve communication difficulties and encourage cooperation among stakeholders and government.

Udujia and Obasib (2018) said that women leading the roles in small-scale fisheries must be included in decision-making activities regarding the conservation and management of fisheries through their participation to General Memoranda of Understanding (GMOUs) via Cluster Development Boards (CDBs). The role of artisanal fisherwomen as stakeholders is important in managing the fisheries resources of Niger Delta region.

The social status of women may be improved through women empowerment and establish more opportunities for involvement in co-management while gender norms also affect this participation as it influences the degree of its acceptability to women (Nunan and Cepic, 2020). The advantages of women participating in co-management groups are the fact that various networks are embodied and accessed by women, specifically, their livelihood in fish trading and processing, and their promotion to protect and support women's livelihoods. Their participation suggests benefits for social and economic development.

According to Gopal et.al. (2020), projects and research focusing on women and gender equality in fisheries and aquaculture lack appropriate funds. Though fisheries and aquaculture are very diverse respective to regions and nations, transformations take place when they are given opportunity to voice out, be heard and be able to choose.

III. STATEMENT OF THE STUDY

The study aims to involve women's perspectives, ideas and opinions in data gathering through consultative questionnaire regarding their involvement in fisheries, what specific sector they are in, their daily activities in that specific sector, production costs, profits gained, the different challenges they encountered and how they have dealt with these situations, including their duties as wives and mothers of the household.

Also, their roles in the community, accomplishments or privileges, their plans in the future and what government interventions they think are necessary to improve their livelihood and community are included in the questionnaire. Their answers will be significant in recognizing further their impact in the household and their groups considering that they do not just work for a living, they also perform duties in the household that is beyond measure.

IV. OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objective of this study is to identify the roles of women in the fishery industry of the municipality of San Fabian in different sectors of capture fisheries, aquaculture, fish processing and fish vending or marketing sector to further show how important the women are in terms of representing the fishery value chain in the municipality.

Eventually, the study will state how the women's livelihood in fishery sector will be improved through identifying possible interventions to be provided for women groups by concerned authorities. It also aims to contribute to literature on the emerging roles of women in the evolving world of fisheries.

V. RATIONALE

Women's role in fisheries is barely recognized for it is stereotyped as work only for men because of its laborious and heavy workload. Nonetheless, the fisheries industry has a broad network of sectors from preparation of fishing paraphernalia, during fishing operation to post-harvest operation which is composed of the preparation of raw products and ingredients, to packaging and marketing of products.

To further identify the roles of women in this sector, this study is done specifically for women fisherfolk in the municipality of San Fabian, Pangasinan. Apart from their typical days at work, the study also acknowledges the unpaid work of women in fulfilling their responsibilities as a mother and a wife to their families. The emerging roles of women to adapt in the changing times and innovative ways to cope up and survive the daily needs of their family will be discussed in the study.

VI. SCOPE AND LIMITATIONS

Women is the only subject of this study. They are the focus of the interview questions relating to their roles in the various sectors of the fishery industry. To identify their roles, questions relating to their typical day at work and in the household were asked. Also, some points on their personal information, their accomplishments, and their plans to provide a description of their roles in the fishery, consequently relating to their roles in the household and the community.

There were only three (3) barangays covered in the municipality of San Fabian, specifically costal barangays where women involvement is dominant. There are 16 interviewees involved in various sectors who participated in the data gathering as identified by fisherfolk leaders and barangay council members.

VII. DESCRIPTION OF THE STUDY AREA

The Municipality of San Fabian is the study area selected. This municipality is a first-class municipality which both involve fisheries and agriculture as main sources of food commodities and livelihood of the residents. It is a coastal municipality in the province of Pangasinan that lies along the Lingayen Gulf. Three (3) barangays were selected that mainly involve women in the fisheries industry, namely Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte, Brgy. Longos Parac-parac and Brgy. Cayanga.

In Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte, women are mainly involved in the capture fisheries and marketing sector. This barangay is a coastal barangay wherein women interviewed are residing few meters away from the coastline. In Brgy. Longos Parac-parac, women are engaged in aquaculture sector and in Brgy. Cayanga, women are involved in fish drying and marketing fishery products. These last two (2) barangays are near to the national road thereby allowing them to market their products more easily.

VIII. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative data will be collected using semi-structured interview methodology and oral history (Hunt 2003 and Jones 2004 as cited by Calhoun et al. 2016). Oral history is done to allow the key informants of the different sectors tell their story without interruptions and overwhelming them with questions while semi-structured interviews aim to gather data based on thematic areas specifically pertaining to their role in fisheries (Calhoun et al. 2016).

To emphasize the roles of women in fisheries, questions are crafted in a broad array of sections that is composed of their typical day at work, challenging experiences, weekly schedules, problems encountered, their plans, and their involvement in organizations in the community. Some personal information such as their age and educational attainment are also included in the questionnaire.

Sixteen (16) respondents of each sector in capture fisheries, aquaculture, fish processing, fish drying, and fish vending were selected through the help of the Municipal Agriculture Office, barangay officials, fisherfolk association leaders and locals in the coastal barangays of San Fabian.

IX. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Roles per Sector

Listed below are the common roles of women gathered during the interview. Total number of respondents are 16 women from three (3) barangays. Majority of women (14 respondents) are from Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte while there are three respondents from Brgy. Longos Parac-parac and one (1) from Brgy. Cayanga. Among the roles for each sector are the following:

1. *Capture Fisheries Sector*

- Capture fishing and shellfish gathering;
- Install fish trap for shrimps, crabs and fish;
- Net mending; and
- Manage profits and expenses for fuel, maintenance, repair, required permits and/or licenses of boat;
- Distribute profits to their crews and allocate the net income for the daily needs of their families. They are boat owners as well.

2. *Aquaculture Sector*

- Hire laborers for the installation of bamboo stakes for fish pen culture of siganids and shellfish culture (oyster);
- Prepare oyster hangings to gather oyster spats;
- Prepare input materials such as bamboo, nets, fingerlings, and feeds;
- Gather natural food or green algae commonly called as “lablab” for cultured stocks; and
- Feed the fish stocks

3. *Fish Processing Sector*

- Drying and salting of fish and other aquatic commodities; one of the most common products in the municipality is the "tuyo" or the dried and salted sardines; tilapia is also dried.
- Milkfish deboning in which one of the respondents is a deboner in a processing plant;
- Value adding of milkfish into boneless marinated bangus, a famous delicacy in the province of Pangasinan;
- Sorting and packing of dried and processed products

4. Fish Vending Sector

- Sell fresh fish/shellfish/shrimp and other fresh commodities, dried fish, processed fish such as boneless marinated bangus; these products are sold to neighborhoods, resorts, wet markets, and transported to other provinces. One of the respondents has a stall along the national road.

B. Typical Day at Work of Women Fisherfolk

For fish vendors, upon arrival of catch from their husbands as fishing boat crews, they sell it to neighborhood or to tourists arriving in each resort. They already have established contacts with resort owners. Usually, their customers are about 10 tourists. If the volume of catch is high, they proceed to the public market. They hire a tricycle to go to the market or walk to every house nearby to sell their goods. Others have their own tri-bikes. When their bikes have malfunctioned, boat crews or owners repair them. After selling the goods, they go back home and take care of their children or grandchildren; and do the common household chores throughout the day. Other respondents said that they also gather firewoods or "panggatong" to save money from using Liquified Petroleum Gas (LPGs) for cooking.

On the other hand, women who operate fish pen culture of siganids purchase ropes, nets, and bamboo for the installation of fish pens. They hire laborers to install bamboo stakes and nets in nearby riverine areas. After the installation, siganid fingerlings are then stocked in fish pens in the months of November to December. During the feeding of stocks, they hire one (1) boat to gather green algae or “lablab” at a nearby riverine area in Brgy. Cayanga. Whenever a boatman is not available, they personally proceed to the area and collect “lablab”. Culture usually takes four (4) months. During their free time, they sell goods at their sari-sari store, as an alternative source of income. Prior to harvest, they prepare containers and purchase ice blocks to maintain the freshness. They hire laborers to haul and transport the harvest through a rented tricycle and then proceed to Magsaysay Market in Dagupan City. Harvest takes place during the months of February to March.

While for the “Tuyo” Makers, they purchase and transport salted fish from Malabon fish port. Fish are contained in rubber basins or “banyeras” transported in trucks. The arrival of trucks of fish in Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte depends on the availability of fish in the fish port. It usually arrives at dawn at about 4AM-5AM. Upon reaching the production area in Sitio Sabangan, Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte, salted fish are washed two to three times. Afterwards, salted fish are arranged in bamboo drying trays or “kalingan” for solar drying or the process locally called “salansan”. Salted fish are dried for 1-2 days depending on the intensity of heat. Dried fish are then packed or “kamada” which typically takes half a day. These are sorted according to their sizes namely, small, medium, large, and low-quality dried fish or those with exposed internal parts. Low quality dried fish is also retailed but at a lower price. Dried fish is wrapped in newspaper and packed in boxes weighing 20 kilograms each. Boxes of dried fish are transported in different provinces of Cordillera such as Tabuk, Kalinga and Baguio City

as well as in the provinces of Ilocos Region namely San Fernando, La Union; Laoag, Ilocos Norte; and Pozorrubio, Pangasinan.

C. Operational Costs

The expenses incurred during each sector's operations are varied. The following are the major requirements or expenses as enumerated by the respondents.

In the capture fisheries, the bulk of operational costs comes from fuel. They use about seven (7) liters of gasoline per sail. They purchase fishing gears and paraphernalia which varies for every season for every fish species caught. Since the boats are made of wood and have an engine, maintenance costs are necessary including the mending of nets and other fishing gears.

In fish pens, operational costs include labor costs for installation of nets and bamboos, boat rentals, cost of feeds and fingerlings, purchase of nets, ropes and bamboo stakes; marketing costs such as ice to maintain the freshness of harvested fish, containers, labor costs for harvesters and rental costs for vehicles during transport.

In the fish processing sector, expenses include cost of raw materials and ingredients, labor costs for fish driers and processors, maintenance of equipment (solar dryers, salting materials), packaging materials (newspapers, boxes) and transportation (vehicle rentals and fuel).

For fish vending, expenses include rental costs for transportation and stalls in the market or stalls along highways.

D. Income and Working Hours

Net income from the abovementioned operational costs varies. The number of working hours required to earn this income also varies because a certain procedure in fish processing such as salting or drying takes a shorter period compared to the number of months of siganid culture requires in the aquaculture sector. For each sector, particulars are enumerated as follows:

1. For capture fisheries sector

Boat owners:

- Net Income is Php2,600
- Gross Income from 1 sail per day = Php3,000
- Fuel cost of Php400
- Number of crews per boat = 5 crews
- Net Average Income for 1 crew per day = Php520
- Number of working hours = 7 hours (6AM-1PM)

Gleaners:

- Net Income from gathering of shellfish: Php300- 500
- Number of working hours per day = 6 hours (6AM-12 NN)
- 6 AM-10AM = gathering
- 10AM-12 NN = transport and selling of goods

2. For fish processing sector

Milkfish Deboner:

- Net take home pay per day is Php400
- Salary from processing plant per day = Php600 (depending on the volume of stocks, they are paid Php2.00 per piece)

- Deductions = Php200 for SSS and PhilHealth contributions (insurance)
- Number of working hours per day = 13 hours (6AM-12NN and 1PM-8 PM whenever there is high volume of fresh milkfish for deboning)

Tuyo Maker:

- Gross Income: Php100,000
- Net Income for 1 drying period (1 week): Php10,000
- Capital: Php80,000 (20 banyeras: 1 banyera of salted fish costs Php4,000) Php10,000 (Cost of labor, delivery of fresh and dried goods, packaging materials)
Total of Php90,000
- Year-round production; however, there are losses especially during rainy season
- Number of working hours per day = 18 Hours (3AM-12NN); Drying period is 2 days including gathering of dried fish and packaging
- Labor fees for women helpers: Php 200 per day

3. *For aquaculture sector*

Siganid Growers:

- Net Income: Php40,000 per cropping (4 months culture period)
- Capital for 1 culture period: Php80,000
- Culture Period: November is the stocking and March is the harvest season
- Sales: Php120,000
- Number of working hours per day: 2 hours (8AM and 12AM feeding time)

Shellfish Growers:

- Net Income: Php1,200-1,500 (10 sacks of oysters at Php120-150 per sack) per cropping (4 months culture period)
- Culture Period: November is the stocking and March is the harvest season
- Additional income from fish traps: Php200 per day
- Number of working hours per day: 3 hours (6AM-9AM)

4. For fish vending sector

Fresh Fish Vendor:

- Net Income per day: Php450
- Capital for buying fresh fish: Php2,250 (15 kg of catch is bought at a price of Php150 per kg)
- Selling price: Php180 per kg
- Gross Income: Php2,700
- Number of working hours per day: 5 hours (6AM-11AM)

Dried Fish vendor (without stall):

- Net Income per day: Php2,000
- Capital for 1 box of tuyo: Php2,000
- Selling price: Php4,000
- Number of working hours per day: 13 hours (4AM-5PM, depending on the arrival of costumers)

Dried Fish vendor (with stall):

- Net Income per day: Php2,000- 20,000 (seasonal)
- Capital: Php100,000-150,000

- Number of working hours per day: 12 hours (6AM-6PM, depending on the arrival of customers from lean to peak seasons)

Table 1

Number of Working Hours and Net Income per Sector and per Role in Daily, Weekly and 4-month Period

Sector and Role	Number of Working Hours	Net Income (Daily, PhP)	Net Income (Weekly, PhP)	Net Income (4-month Period, PhP)
Boat owner	7	520	-	-
Gleaner	6	400	-	-
Deboner	13	400	-	-
Tuyo-Making (Owner)	36	-	10,000	-
Female Worker (Tuyo-Making)	18	200	-	-
Siganid Grower	120	-	-	40,000
Shellfish Grower	120	-	-	1,200
Fresh Fish Vendor	5	450	-	-
Dried Fish Vendor (no stall)	13	2,000	-	-
Dried Fish Vendor (with stall)	12	11,000	-	-

X. ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

The summary of working hours corresponding to the net income per role is mentioned in Table 1. Each sector has its own reasonable income, however, based on the amount of income and number of working hours or efforts spent, it was observed that the aquaculture, dried fish vending and fish processing sector are more profitable than capture fisheries. Dried fish vending with stalls is less laborious, however, it required more capital since this specific sector will need more volume and variety of dried goods as well as rental costs of the stall.

Aquaculture sector, installation of bamboo stakes and nets required heavy workload, less work is done during the culture period since feeding is routinary and less exhausting. Nevertheless, same as dried fish vending, more capital is necessary but guarantees more profit. This sector as well as the fish processing also require manpower, hence, additional labor costs.

Considering that the capture fisheries sector is more laborious and riskier, less capital is needed since the boat and the fishing gear used will last for several years and no rental fees are required.

Source of capital can be noted as one of the limiting factors why women fisherfolk stay on fresh fish vending and capture fisheries sector, considering their traditional knowledge and skills in fishing operation acquired from their families and the environment they live in.

Most women fisherfolk performed roles covering all sectors mentioned. This implied that women are considered “Jack of all trades”. They perform multiple roles based on factors such as seasonality of catch, weather condition and available resources and opportunities in their community.

Among all phases of fish production in rural and coastal regions, women are present, including processing and distribution, generation of funds, aquatic ecosystem preservation, maintenance of households and communities. They perform major roles in aquaculture and fisheries economies worldwide, contributing to a half of the workforce (The World Bank, 2012 as cited in Gopal et.al. 2020; FAO, 2018). However, their work is not recognized officially in records such as in statistics, policies in various sectors and programs for development (Gopal et.al. 2020).

Apart from their roles in fisheries, managing their households is a part of their daily role as housewives, taking care of the children, budgeting expenses and educating their children particularly during the pandemic when they are unable to go to schools. Thus, these efforts are invaluable.

According to the Philippine Commission on Women, women have their own multiple burdens with their unpaid work of taking care for their children, elders and members of the family who are ill. To provide their families with additional income, they must be productive and at the same time do their care work. This is the reason why they have shorter rest periods and higher stress. The closure of schools during the pandemic had an additional impact on their works since they should be second teachers to their children by guiding and monitoring their academic performance (Philippine Commission on Women, n.d.).

Most of the respondents did not finish tertiary level of education. They had their own families at an early age. This means that they must have an immediate source of livelihood, income, and support to be able to feed their families.

The roles of women take a long period of time in a day which starts from administering the household, arranging the necessities of their spouses prior to sail, assembly and mending of nets, and when the husband comes back, women now sort,

clean, and sell the catch. With that consumed time, she is unable to enjoy the rewards of her work since everything is performed as a help to the husband (Wahyuni, 2022).

Fisherman’s wives, their partners, and daughters, in a fishing community usually do not have formal employment status. Their responsibilities range in multiple tasks such as bookkeepers and/or accountants, crews’ cooks, drivers, representatives for gatherings and meetings, community administrators or organizers and many others (Zhao et.al. 2013).

When asked about their income, particularly for capture fisheries and fresh fish vending sector, the majority said that they had their produce only for daily sustenance. This made them unable to have the privilege to finish studies or support their children for secondary or tertiary education, nor to provide comfortable homes for their families.

Despite lacking privileges in education and funds for necessities, they still had their plans and dreams for their families to improve their way of life. Among these are to have convenient and safe homes, profitable businesses, stable source of livelihood, and successful children in terms of achievements in their careers.

Table 2

List of Issues Encountered and the Corresponding Interventions Possible to be Provided to Women Fisherfolk and Their Fishing Communities

No.	Issues and constraints encountered	Possible Interventions
1	Low catch	Campaign for information and awareness to fisheries conservation; provision of sustainable fishing gears and paraphernalia such as hook and line and prohibition for illegal and destructive fishing gears
2	Lack of logistics for transport of goods and climate resilient facilities for drying	Provision of equipment for drying, support to repair and maintenance of fishing paraphernalia, establishment of subsidized ice plants; fish carts and fish stalls

No.	Issues and constraints encountered	Possible Interventions
3	Unstable income and source of alternative livelihood	Training and livelihood support not just for technical capabilities but also social and values enhancement to facilitate behavioral change
4	Unstable areas of residence (lots not owned)	Safe and comfortable housing facilities; minimal rental fees to instill their sense of responsibility and ownership
5	Lack of funds for capital in putting up a business; support to inputs (fishing paraphernalia, fuel, feeds)	Credit opportunities with low interest rates; training on financial literacy; counter parting schemes to advocate responsible handling of funds
6	Health privileges	Insurance opportunities, free or subsidized hospitalization
7	Lack of opportunities in education	More options for scholarships and regular promotion of these opportunities, free education from primary to secondary
8	Natural calamities (typhoon, earthquake, strong waves, and winds)	Support to disaster readiness and awareness, comfortable evacuation centers with facilities and provisions

Most of the possible interventions identified are existing programs and projects of the government through various agencies such as the BFAR or the Bureau of Fisheries and Aquatic Resources mandated for the welfare of fisherfolk by increasing the resiliency and production in aquaculture and fisheries, adaptation of technologies that are appropriate and science-based, and by having projects, programs and policies that are socially inclusive, gender responsive (bfar.da.gov.ph). The agency also promotes Fisherfolk Scholarship Program among other agencies with scholarship opportunities such as the Department of Science and Technology (DOST).

In an article published by Gaerlan et.al. (2012), one of these projects is the GAD or the Gender and Development Project which assists RICs or the Rural Improvement Clubs. Nine (9) RICs were assisted by BFAR through provision of processing and post-

harvest materials such as knives, deboning kits, smoking chambers, freezers, stoves, chopping boards, trays, basins, measuring equipment, tables, and chairs. The agency also conducted training and capacity building activities to develop their skills in fish deboning and be oriented on the gender and development and GMP/SSOP or the Good Manufacturing Practices and Sanitation Standards Operating Procedures. The activity also included values formation, leadership, management, simple bookkeeping, and financial management to strengthen the organization.

These groups in Calasiao and Labrador in the province of Pangasinan; Sudipen, Paraoir and Rosario in La Union; Sta. Cruz and Sto. Domingo in Ilocos Sur; Vintar and Batac in Ilocos Norte, were the beneficiaries of the project under the post-harvest and livelihood. Members of the association also participated in “Lakbay-Aral” or field trips in successful establishments of fish processing plants producing fish paste “bagoong” and milkfish products namely, the Anjo Farms Incorporated located in San Fabian, Pangasinan. With the help of the Local Government Unit Counterparts, these projects helped RICs generate additional income and improve their livelihood sources through the establishment of temporary food processing centers. Aside from BFAR’s intervention, the Department of Trade and Industry also assisted through their expertise in marketing and trade, and the DOST through developing the labels of their products.

For the housing facilities, the DHSUD or the Department of Human Settlements and Urban Development which is the key agency mandated for the human settlement, management of housing, and urban development and also performs oversight functions on its attached key shelter agencies such as the NHA or the National Housing Authority which acts as the agency in-charge of the production of shelters, and the Pag-IBIG Fund or the Home Development Mutual Fund which is mandated for

the reasonable shelter funding and savings program for Filipino workers (dhsud.gov.ph).

For financing institutions, one of the government institutions mandated is the Landbank of the Philippines which has expanded its loan portfolio for its priority sectors such as the small farmers and fisherfolk, and the agri- and aqua-projects of the Local Government Units (landbank.com). Also, the Philippine Crop Insurance Corporation (PCIC) is the primary provider of agricultural insurance program from arising natural calamities including non-crop agricultural assets such as machineries, transport facilities, etc (pcic.gov.ph).

The PCW or the Philippine Commission on Women is the major policy-making agency in-charge of coordinating concerns of women and gender equality and in upgrading the status of women particularly gender mainstreaming, women's authority, and empowerment. The Republic Act No. 9170 or the "Magna Carta of Women" declares that the "State shall take steps to review and, when necessary, amend and/or repeal existing laws that are discriminatory to women". The PCW then is tasked to monitor the implementation of the said law and guarantee that agencies in the government can make it effective. The PCW introduced the WPLA or the Women's Priority Legislative Agenda, a publicly consulted array of proposed subjects of bills, that aims to repeal or amend the provisions of existing laws that are discriminatory. This agenda also pursues the invention and adoption of new legislation that endorse, defend, and realize the empowerment and rights of women (pcw.gov.ph).

The FAO or the Food and Agriculture Organization and several agencies in the United Nations are promoting gender equality in aquaculture and fisheries which have resulted to improved productivity, income, decreased losses in post-harvest, enhanced nutrition and food security and upgraded management of natural resources with the help of women's empowerment (Macusi et.al. 2022).

FAO, together with other countries elaborates gender-responsive and comprehensive policies and programs that support fisheries sustainability and growth in aquaculture through efforts in reversing gender-blind policies. This ensures that the needs and differences of women, are attended and that they have equal rights in accessing resources and opportunities to decent employment. FAO also promotes women's engagement by investing in communities in the fisheries field, upgrading the system of trade and innovations on the institutional arrangements for management. This means that FAO ensures the engagement of women in decision-making procedures in the sectors of aquaculture and fisheries (fao.org).

Since several issues and constraints were already identified and are existing then and now, proposed interventions should also be evaluated and eventually be improved through inclusive and combined efforts from the women sector, public and private institutions. Mentioned agencies are some of the numerous agencies mandated for the welfare of women, and their programs should be maximized and be implemented effectively, to bring sustainable and impactful outcomes for the betterment of women. These are just three of various government and non-government agencies which support the welfare of women not just in fisheries but in many aspects of their livelihood and empowerment. Through the Gender and Development Programs, existing projects that are already implemented and future programs that are being formulated are anchored into making sure that women participate and involve in all sorts of interventions.

XI. RECOMMENDATION AND CONCLUSION

The roles of women in fisheries covers very diverse and wide range of duties and occupations. They perform roles such as fish processors specifically salting, drying, smoking, deboning, marinating, value-adding, sorting, and packing, fish farmers, retailers and traders, gleaners, managers of boats in terms of finances and they also repair nets, buy fishing paraphernalia, prepare logistics, and assist in fishing operation among others. Apart from these, they prepare food for their families, take care of the children, gather firewood, buy necessities in the household, clean the house, budget their income and other common duties of being a wife and a mother. These roles make them a significant part of the pre-operation activities in fishing, and post-fishing, rendering them to complete the processes in the value chain of fisheries produce and their very significant role of being the light of the household.

Organizing and strengthening groups of women bring out more tangible achievements. They make innovations and adapt to the demands of the market. They manage to perform multitasks that make them flexible and skillful in any given role. These scenarios develop strong leadership in the women sector. Therefore, efforts to support women empowerment in fisheries should be enhanced through partnerships and capability building activities.

Women are important partners in fisheries industry. Identification of their roles and recognition of these help them upgrade their skills and uplift their morals. A strong and skilled woman produce an empowered community. This will also promote awareness of their significance and priceless efforts to cope to multiple burdens not just in the household but also in the fishery industry and women workforce.

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APPENDICES

Appendix A. Photos taken during the interview of Women fisherfolk along Coastal Barangays of San Fabian, Pangasinan.

1. Photo with Ms. Elvira Salcedo of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is engaged in fish vending and fish drying.

2. Photo with Ms. Maricar Mabanglo of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a vendor of dried and fresh fish.

3. Photo with Ms. Guia Salcedo of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a boat owner and in-charge of managing the operational costs of a motorized fishing boat.

4. Photo with Ms. Cindy Imbornal of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a vendor of fresh fish to tourists in different resorts in San Fabian.

5. Photo with Ms. Angelita Naraja of Brgy. Longos Parac-parac. She is engaged in capture fishing. She owns fish traps and sells the catch. At the left is Ms. Jovielyn Barrozo, Brgy. Councilor.

6. Photo with Ms. Lolita Naraja of Brgy. Longos Parac-parac. She is engaged in oyster culture, fresh fish and shellfish vending.

7. Photo with Ms. Rosalinda Narvas of Brgy. Longos Parac-parac. She is engaged in siganids culture and fish vending.

8. Photo with Ms. Carolyn Castro of Brgy. Cayanga. She is a dried fish vendor and fish processor.

9. Photo with Ms. Fina Imbornal of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a boat owner, fish vendor and also a college student.

10. Photo with Ms. Ester Orjeda of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a fish vendor.

11. Photo with Ms. Venusca Abong and Ms. Via Abong of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. Ms. Via is the daughter of Ms. Venusca and they are both involved in fish vending, fish drying and capture fishing.

12. Photo with Ms. Lerio Lomandas of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a milkfish deboner employed in a fish processing plant.

13. Photo with Ms. Sylvia Imbornal of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a fish vendor and engaged in gleaning of seashells.

14. Photo with Ms. Evelyn Imbornal of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a “tuyo” maker.

15. Photo with Ms. Janice Urbino of Brgy. Nibaliw Narvarte. She is a fish vendor and engaged in gleaning of seashells.